

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE POWERED HEALTHCARE APPLICATION: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a worldwide phenomenon with diverse advents in a variety of fields. AI has potential to ease human resource crisis in healthcare enabling diagnostics, decision-making, big data analytics and administration. Applications of AI make healthcare cost-efficient and making medical processes more effective. Healthcare needs real-time, actionable insights and support doctors to the patient treatment process enhanced by the interconnectivity of devices over faster networks. Some of the key areas where AI can have significant influence are patient administration, patient monitoring, clinical decision support, and healthcare information integration. Specifically, the AI-enabled system would gather data, process, and help real-time intelligent decision making. This article discusses the remarkable practical benefits of AI applications in the healthcare sector through 5 G-enabled networks in the era of COVID-19. Also, relevant challenges that need further research to secure the future of AI-enabled and efficient healthcare system in developing countries is discussed.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Healthcare, Patients, COVID-19, Developing Countries

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Apart from the inconvenience, frustrating registration process, appointments and more of one-size-for-all medical treatment system, the overcrowded healthcare facilities with overloaded medical staff, lack of medical equipment, and shortage of medical staff are common features of the healthcare industry in most of the developing countries. The aforementioned issues are exacerbated by a disparity in healthcare resources, a lack of quality infrastructure, and the difficulty for rural patients to access urban healthcare facilities. (Dahri, Hameed, Nawaz, Sami, & Bux, 2019). In addition, non-individualized diagnosis and treatment models, and non-holistic data-driven healthcare practice model rather than past trial-and-error experience-based patient treatment practices are major problems faced by most developing countries albeit the availability of 21st century state of the art Artificial Intelligence-enabled Internet of Things (IoT) devices that can be connected over multiple networks (Dahri, &Thebo, 2020)

The advancement in wireless technology and machine learning have enabled various businesses to develop new business models to satisfy customers and end-users needs

particularly during the recent COVID-19 pandemic. Besides that, progress in fog and mobile edge computing has strengthened 5G significantly (Zhang, Ma, Zhang, Hossain, Muhammad, & Amin, 2019) to enable the first layer of data production to be processed by ultra-latency communication. In addition to this, edge-based processing is energy and cost-efficient for data transfer. Fog and mobile edge computing are anticipated to be able run the heavy real-time data at network edge by openly utilizing the billions of linked mobile devices.

The 5G wireless technology comprises of three core components that allow low latency to handle a huge number of IoT platforms and provide faster bitrate. Due to problems like COVID-19, the advantages of 5G can be further elevated using diverse edge devices with scalability and insightful response to dynamic networks (Chamola, Hassija, Gupta, & Guizani, 2020). These can be tailored for healthcare services especially for pandemic related cases such as COVID-19 where mobile broadband, large dataset exchange, device-to-device connectivity can be integrated. As 5G can handle a large number of healthcare mobile IoTs, one of its applications can be for people who wish to leave the places of quarantine or commute between places. They can send a message and get a current map with pandemic status and authorities can guide and track them if they fall ill or the person whom they contacted feels sick.

With advancements in cloud computing coupled with massive healthcare data processing tools, Artificial intelligence (AI) stands as one of the core enablers for smarter, safer, and better patients' digital healthcare experience at the lowest cost and highest reach. With 5G networks, AI helps build a customized and safer mobile IoT healthcare ecosystem in developed and developing countries.

AI is a hot research area that is intensively investigated since the 1950s (Hashem, Yaqoob, Anuar, Mokhtar, Gani, & Khan, 2015). Alan Turing defined AI as machine intelligence capable to demonstrate human-like behaviors (Priyanka & Sanjay, 2015) with the ability to simulate human intelligence and behaviors (Basma, Hajar&Abdelkrim, 2016) leading to the 4th industrial revolution. As compared to the past, the current era holds a tremendous amount of data that may drive AI to its full potential. As such, companies are funding heavily for real-world AI applications in various fields related to the healthcare industry (Raul, Patil, Raheja&Sawant, 2016).

2.0 HEALTHCARE AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPLICATION

Mahmud & Parkhurst (2007) asserted that healthcare sector enables the economic expansion of a given country. To unlock this potential, countries globally assembled human resources and financial institutions to deliver better healthcare services that meet population needs particularly in developing countries (Mills, 2014). The World Health Organization (WHO) sets a minimum standard for the countries to spend 5% (Cassels & Janovsky, 1998) had allocated a \$142.6 million budget for developing countries to achieve set targets which sadly no country could achieve (Bernaert & Dimitrova, 2017). Besides that, Neil (2013) found that high priced drugs, disease proliferation, failure of care delivery, skyrocketing healthcare costs, and hospital-acquired infection had caused adverse effects. These are the reasons why the

healthcare system needs an informed, effective, efficient, and intelligent system that supports decisions and treatment processes for clinicians and patients.

Significant progress has been observed in AI and its applications particularly in the healthcare sector (Huang, Lan, Fang, An, Min & Wang, 2015). Therefore, some medical practices that are currently served by clinicians and healthcare administrators will be taken over by AI (Wang, Kung & Byrd, 2018). The prospective role of AI methods and techniques to deliver better healthcare service and in medical research is becoming ever more evident (Ramesh, Kambhampati, Monson & Drew, 2004). Many types of research have revealed the efficiency and potential of AI-based healthcare applications. This technical development is also supported by substantial investments in the AI-based applications for the healthcare sector by both governments and technology based companies (Miliard, 2018). From theoretical to practical view, AI applications can apply to almost every area of healthcare service. According to Rock Health, a leading venture capital firm, around 121 healthcare-based AI and machine learning firms raised \$2.7 billion between 2011 and 2017 (Kanevsky, Corban, Gaster, Kanevsky, & Lin, 2016).

AI can use a sophisticated algorithm to ‘learn’ from large volumes of healthcare data and then use this data for informed clinical practices. Moreover, the AI system reduces human errors in the diagnosis (Pearson, 2011) and excerpts significant information from a large patient database to support real-time implications for healthcare outcome predictions (Neill, 2013). Similarly, according to World Economic Forum (2020), Carla Kriwet, the Chief Executive Officer, BSH Hausgeräte GmbH reported AI will transform healthcare by 2030 in terms of access to data from multiple sources to reveal diseases patterns and treatment cure methods, will predict illness of individuals at risk of catching a disease, and aid in efficiency by reducing patient waiting time. In light of the overwhelming potential scope of AI integrated healthcare system, the healthcare administration, clinical decision support, patient monitoring are the most influenced areas in healthcare. In addition, potential areas of AI application in healthcare related to covid-19 pandemic and mass surveillance are emerging interests.

2.1 Healthcare Administration

Since the healthcare services are restrained due to scarce resources and complex infrastructure in many countries particularly from the administrative perspective (Wells, 2017). In this respect, AI and data mining techniques are heavily invested to support the healthcare system and augment clinical care by lessening administrative demands on clinicians (Snyder, Wu, Miller, Jensen, Bantug & Wolff, 2011). Such that, by taking routine tasks, for instance, entry of patient’s data, review of laboratory data, and analyze imaging results, AI can save a lot of time for healthcare practitioners to provide direct care for patients (Derrington, 2017).

In the same way, more time can be saved and search accuracy can be improved through the use of machine learning and concept-based information retrieval system. Further, integration between machine learning algorithms and electronic healthcare record can assist the healthcare practitioners to get accurate and most relevant information about patients (Saria, 2014). Besides, it is asserted that the implementation of the optimized machine learning algorithms

supports healthcare service provides in the patients' prioritization and clinical scheduling (Huang, Jennings & Fox, 1995) and by gathering electronic health record documentation and clinical notes as leave-taking (Leventhal, 2017) would reduce wait times and increase services efficiency.

2.2 Clinical Decision Support

Clinical decision support (CDS) systems as per Musen (2006) are computer programs, which allow healthcare practitioners to make a decision based on the extracted clinical data and knowledge. CDS systems, thus, reduce clinical inaccuracies and enhance healthcare efficiency and consistency. Consequently, within healthcare, the integration and use of CDS systems are increasing in the routine practices of healthcare practitioners. Therefore, AI techniques are utilized in CDS system research since the 1970s as an expert system.

Furthermore, the use of machine learning algorithms has now been extended to envision the occurrence of septic shock diagnosis (Saria, 2014), for the treatment of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients, and several other key decisions (Anakal & Sandhya, 2017). These algorithms can make treatment decisions personalized for each patient based on the large scale of past cases that otherwise were difficult to integrate into clinical decision making. For example, AI could infer a patient's health, suggest alternate ways for treatment, and improve exiting treatment plans based on new information received (Reddy, Sandeep, John Fox, & Purohit, 2019).

With the advancement of machine learning and Clinical Decision Support (CDS) system benefits, this potential expands enormously through a neural network which is an advanced step of machine learning with more promising future. AI neural networks based CDS system deploys superior capabilities in predicting medical illnesses like cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes risks and histopathological diagnosis. AI neural networks potentially detect gaps in the treatment protocols and diminish prospective errors (Medrano, Guijarro, Belda, Ureña Salcedo, Anke, & Saggion, 2018).

2.3 Patient Monitoring

The implementation of electronic health records and the rise of Smartphone's and fitness monitoring devices open the doorway to digital data enabling AI technique exploitation to monitor patients (Saria, 2014) by providing detailed information about patients ranging from sleep patterns to electroencephalographs, electromyography, and Doppler ultrasounds in hospitals (Ramesh et al, 2004). Figure 1 elaborates on 10 types of diseases which are able to be diagnosed through AI.

Figure 1: Ten types of disease detected in Artificial Intelligence (AI) literature

Source: Jiang, F., Jiang, Y., Zhi, H., Dong, Y., Li, H., Ma, S., & Wang, Y. (2017).

Moreover, AI enables software in the hospitals can be used in intensive care units (ICU) to monitor a patient’s vital signs of the cardiovascular and respiratory system. Further, once the patient visits the hospital, the patient’s health and medical information can be managed through a natural language processing virtual assistant (Ramesh et al., 2004). The utilization of discussed virtual health assistants are proven to be resourceful for reliably increasing the medication compliance and follow-up (Contreras & Vehi, 2018).

2.4 Other Potential Areas of AI Application in Healthcare

The use of AI in the healthcare sector has been found as a relatively new research area, which merges realistic and computational techniques with the vision of expert physicians to introduce tools to improve healthcare services. The central idea of AI is to bring advancement in computers by making them more viable and capable to understand the ideas that make intelligence realistic.

In recent years, a notable development in computer vision and robotics promise cost-effective diagnostic and faster treatments (Fabrizio, Termine, Caltagirone, & Sancesario, 2021). For instance, computer vision is deployed in healthcare to build 3D images (Szeliski, 2011) and to assess patient’s conditions by facial recognition through facial recognition analysis (Thevenot, López & Hadid, 2018). For example, many elderly patients may have little medical care and attention which is a great opportunity to utilize robots in the healthcare where robots can help them regarding regular activities and guide them through unaware environments (Pollack, Brown, Colbry, Orosz, Peintner, Ramakrishnan, & Thrun, 2002).

Similarly, other examples include, natural language processing that enables map creation about patient conditions and provides personalized experience (Xiao, Choi, & Sun, 2018). Likewise, the real-time advanced alert systems about patients can be deployed and healthcare practitioners can utilize these signals and can timely respond to unpredicted changes as needed (Paulson, Dummett, Green, Scruth, Reyes, & Escobar, 2020). AI algorithms that can process billions of trials in a short time can be used for predictive analysis for symptoms of dangerous

diseases such as cancer and be helpful for both patients and doctors leading to the effective utilization of limited healthcare resources (Wang, Kung & Byrd, 2018).

The aforementioned areas related to healthcare do not restrict the enormous potential of AI-enabled healthcare applications some other examples for areas of AI application in healthcare are as follows:

- AI can go beyond traditional healthcare service areas. For example, machine learning can be utilized to speed up drug development and market entry (Saria, 2014); AI can be used for syndromic surveillance on disease outbreaks (Chen & Zeng, 2014); and to anticipate health outcomes for critical cancer patients (Ramesh et al., 2004).
- Readmission reduction. A good healthcare system can reduce the number of readmissions efficiently and be more patient-centric. Healthcare practitioners can obtain daily updates regarding patient readmission and the ways through which the risk of readmission can be reduced.
- Reduce patient length of stay (LOS): Health systems can reduce LOS by monitoring treatment stages and improve satisfaction by identifying which patients may need longer to stay at the hospital.
- Predict the development of the disease: AI using machine learning can predict potential disease symptoms in patients and track misdiagnosed or undiagnosed patients' chronic diseases and present patient-specific prevention interventions.

2.4.1 COVID-19 and Artificial Intelligence

Before COVID-19, one of the biggest challenges healthcare organizations faced was how to accelerate and scale their application of AI, both clinically and operationally. Now, the COVID-19 cases that emerge globally during the pandemic are revealing AI's potential for optimizing value (Nicole & Cotiviti, 2020). Global pandemic like COVID-19 created an unexpected boost in tele-health visits estimated from 36 million for 2020 to 1 billion over 200 different countries trying to address varying effects of COVID-19 (OECD, 2020). Integration of remotely interconnected smart devices and apps powered by AI is critical in the healthcare sector (Dahri & Maitlo, 2020, Dahri & Thebo, 2020). Specifically, technology trends such as virtual healthcare management and telemedicine are providing decisive role to fight COVID-19 (Pradeep, 2020).

For instance, NCS deployed AI-powered thermal cameras in Singapore addressing the shortage of manpower at healthcare facilities for manual one-to-one temperature checking. Followed by the Robotic Process Automation (RPA) to reduce manual entry-exit data recording at Community Care Facilities (CCF). These robots and video surveillance systems help to sense signs of temperature, heart rate, sound and gesture for contactless cough detection (NCS, 2020).

2.4.2 Mass Surveillance

This idea is closely applicable in the healthcare system, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Hospitals and governments can track confirmed COVID-19 patients' temperature,

movement locations, and close contact people through the 5G connected mobile IoT devices using AI-enabled application (refer Figure 2). These devices will help generate maps of confirmed COVID-19 patient movement, areas of a suspected infection outbreak, potential hot areas, and those areas which are still safe.

Figure 2: AI-powered smart glasses are finding people with corona virus in China

Source: (Thomas Macaulay, March 26, 2020).

3.0 Challenges of AI in Healthcare: Methodology and Findings

AI brings along much challenges albeit it's wide application and huge potential in the healthcare industry. Applying AI to real-world health-care problems is a time-consuming process that entails resolving a slew of issues that extend beyond constructing AI models that can map inputs to outputs. The authors conducted a literature study using Connected Papers (<https://www.connectedpapers.com/>) to find literature reviews of the field of AI in healthcare to identify the challenges and sub-challenges. According to Tay (2021), Connected Papers is a easy to use and powerful tool that promises to help researchers quickly identify similar papers with just one "seed paper" (a relevant paper) and further on help to detect seminal papers as well as review papers. A quick review using Google identified a website Analytics India Magazine that chronicles technological progress in the space of analytics, artificial intelligence, data science & big data by highlighting the innovations, players, and challenges (refer <https://analyticsindiamag.com/>). A particular article dated 26th May 2021 entitled Challenges and Future of AI in Healthcare was uncovered as deemed as worthy to be used as the seed paper for Connected Papers. The articles generated various challenges concerning AI in Healthcare: (1) the huge pressure on healthcare systems and equipment, (2) exponential growth of healthcare data, (3) producing perfect insights at the point of decision making, (4) augmented intelligence for the clinicians, and (5) ethical and legal challenges (AIM, 2021). The aforementioned challenges are consistent with the views of Dr. Tina Manoharan from the Global Lead Data Science and AI Center of Excellence and Digital Research Division at Philips based on an interview with Tech Talks (Dickson, 2021). Connected Papers was used again to identify the sub-challenges using keywords from each challenge as the seed paper. Table 2 presents the findings.

Table 2: Challenges, Sub-challenges in Implementing Healthcare-based AI

No.	Challenges	Sub-challenges	Authors
1	Huge pressure on healthcare systems and equipment	Integrating machine learning (e.g. neural networks and deep learning) in healthcare systems and equipment Training and competency of experts	Dahri, A. S., & Thebo, L. A. (2020). Ishnoor Kaur, T. Bahi, L. Ajeya, H. Rahman, Arun Kumar, S. Arora, I. Bulbul (2021). Kelly, C. J., Karthikesalingam, A., Suleyman, M., Corrado, G. and King, D.(2019)
2	Exponential growth of healthcare data	Lack of integrated tools (e.g. IoT) for data processing and information assessment for patient management.	Dahri, A. S., & Thebo, L. A. (2020). Kelly, C. J., Karthikesalingam, A., Suleyman, M., Corrado, G. and King, D.(2019)
3	Produce perfect insights at the point of decision making	Lack of clinician input and data bottlenecks Lack of expertise to build intuitive tools that can easily integrate with clinical workflow	Dahri, A. S., & Thebo, L. A. (2020). Kent (2020)
4	Augmented intelligence for the clinicians	Reluctance of clinicians to use technology such as augmented intelligence which is a design pattern for a human-centered partnership model of people and AI working together to enhance mental performance, learning, decision making and new experiences.	Dahri, A. S., & Thebo, L. A. (2020). Mahajan (2019) Long & Ehrenfeld.(2020)
5	Ethical and legal challenges	Ethical: (1) informed consent to use, (2) safety and transparency, (3) algorithmic fairness and biases, and (4) data privacy Legal: (1) safety and effectiveness, (2) liability, (3) data protection and privacy, (4) cybersecurity, and (5) intellectual property law	Cohen I.G. (2018) Price W.N., II, Cohen I.G. (2019) Price W.N., II (2017) Wexler R. (2018) Minssen T., Getke S., Abov, M., Price N., Cohen I.G. (2020), Froomkin A.M., Kerr I., Pineau J. (2019)

CONCLUSIONS

This article provides a general view of the AI-enabled influences and 5G network developments in the healthcare system. It shows the impact that AI holds over major areas of the healthcare sector. This article highlights the challenges and future potential of AI-enabled healthcare system specifically in developing countries. Indeed, AI-enabled 5G network holds the power to tackle enormous digital data of healthcare regarding patient and their treatment.

Further, AI analytics and machine learning disease predictability can save millions of lives globally. AI technology will reduce human errors and human effort at most cost-effective and efficient rates while, integration of data and AI devices together through the internet would overcome the shortage of skilled workforce cost-effectively and efficiently which is one of the most serious concerns of the healthcare system in developing countries (Liang et al., 2019), such as Pakistan (Naseem, Rashid, &Kureshi, 2014).

Besides technical and cost-effective advantages, the AI system simplifies tasks for clinicians, nurses, doctors, physicians, administration, and stakeholders. However, decisions based on AI could be complex and vague for which AI systems should be bias-free, easy to understand,

real-life relevance and user-friendly interface experience, and readily adaptable for any field. For which government investment, innervations, and policy development need to meet the cautions and careful planning. Therefore, it is immensely important to grow research in different fields and contexts that customizes incredible AI potential for the efficient use of scarce resources.

AI in these healthcare domains is not whether the technologies will be capable enough to be useful, but rather ensuring their adoption in daily clinical practice. For widespread adoption to take place, AI systems must be approved by regulators, integrated with EHR systems, standardised to a sufficient degree that similar products work in a similar fashion, taught to clinicians, paid for by public or private payer organisations and updated over time in the field.

The technological adoption in the healthcare paced the information flow between doctor and patient pilling up twice every three years for which an estimated reading time for physician to remain up to date is 29 hours straight which is impossible (Curioni-Fontecedro, 2017). The healthcare information technology (HIT) development holds potential to improve healthcare quality and accuracy in emergency, safety, medical errors, efficiency, and patient care (Rothenhaus et al., 2009). Therefore, the immediate innovative intervention is needed in rural areas of developing countries (Samad, Al-Athwari, & Hussain, 2019). This adds critical call for more advanced computational power to smart devices used in healthcare system such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) agents to enhance the predictiveness in healthcare workflow (Bui, 2000), improve quality and lower costs for patient care. Where, managers could use medical equipment and new technological tools to improve patient safety and satisfaction (Birgani & Asadpoor, 2011).

Typically, in developing countries like Pakistan, hospital-acquired infections are themselves a big killer (Dahri&Thebo, 2020). Thus, hospital management could deploy devices that monitor medical professional within hospital and patients out of hospital vicinities. For example, M-IoT based hygiene monitoring system could save million patients, time of doctors, and efficiently manage the resources. This can be reflected in current COVID-19 pandemic, where global system in all respects has collapsed, specifically the healthcare sector. And failure of healthcare is currently approximated to failure of the state machinery.

Therefore, the future of healthcare, even in emergency department, performance typically relies on connectivity of smart devices over the internet, and the transfer of information is crucial for any developed as well as developing countries like Pakistan (Dahri & Thebo, 2020). This research beacons the AI enabled M-IoT adoption in healthcare to benefit masses with high accuracy, effectiveness and efficiency.

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